

IMPACT DAMAGE ANALYSIS OF OPTICAL FIBRES IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: It is commonly reported that within nominal guidelines, embedding optical fibres in composite materials has little effect on the overall structural integrity of the component. This paper will report on the suitability of embedding Optical Fibres (OF) in commonly used carbon-fibre composites. These panels will be designed, manufactured and tested for the effects of typical fibre-optic geometrical and physical parameters such as types of fibre coating polymers, fibre diameter and fibre distribution. Based on impact tests on Optical Fibres-embedded composites, it is shown that significant deterioration on strength is observed beyond a certain OF density level. This paper will focus on the macroscopic effect of having optical fibres in composites from a structural integrity and impact damage point-of-view. To this end, an exposition on the theoretical considerations using continuum mechanics and fracture energy release-rate principles is provided.

KEY TERMS: Optical fibres, damage, impact, resin-rich, strain-energy

INTRODUCTION

One of the key issues to be addressed in this paper is the embedding of Optical Fibres in composite structures and its effect on the material properties of the laminated composite. Future aerospace applications can be expected to require structures with ever lower weight and higher temperature and strength capabilities. Composite materials offer a potential means of enabling these structural properties but manufacturing difficulties and adequate methods of verifying structural integrity has slowed their development.

Optical Fibres sensors may be embedded directly into the material and used to monitor the manufacturing process. The same Optical Fibres sensors may be used in conjunction with nondestructive evaluation methods to evaluate the integrity of parts once they have been manufactured to check for flaws that may result from processing or handling. Once the parts have been installed into the structure, the sensors may be interconnected into a health monitoring network that could be used to determine maintenance requirements and operational readiness.

Benefits of using 'Smart' structure technology include safe and reliable structures giving optimum performance under varying conditions with minimal human interference. Since the concept is in the embryonic stage, a number of technical issues need to be addressed before successful applications become a reality.

Mechanical testing of composite panels with Optical Fibres was undertaken to determine the tensile strength. Some of the details are described below but the comprehensive overview of this experimental program can be obtained from Hadzic (2000).

The verification of experimental and computational results was undertaken through the development of the theoretical models of optimum optical fibre embeddability and spatial distribution. Here, an exposition on the theoretical considerations using continuum mechanics and energy principles is provided.

MACROMECHANICAL EXPERIMENTS

The effects of embedded Optical Fibres (OF) on the mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy composite as a host material were studied. Optical Fibres, 125/250 μm in diameter were embedded in AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy and Fibredux 914 unidirectional carbon pre-pregs. The static performance of the material was evaluated. The Optical fibres were placed in the mid-plane and near the surface of the specimens both parallel to the loading direction. Table 1 below shows the dimensions and it explains the laminate identification used to define the lay-up and the Optical Fibre placement.

Introduction

The approach taken in this work, conducting static tests on laminates with embedded Optical Fibres, is not new. Various workers such as Culshaw and Gardiner (1993) found it is possible to choose composite host systems with embedded OF sensors that do not have degraded static mechanical properties.

Transverse tensile (90^0) testing on two different host materials produced different results in their study. One material produced failures at the OF inclusion while the other did not. Longitudinal (0^0) compression strengths were reduced when the OF were embedded orthogonally.

Experimental Procedure

In the first part of the experimental program, composite laminates were made from commercial AS4/3501-6 (carbon epoxy) tape from Hercules Inc. The prepreg stacks were laminated as eight $[(90/0^0)_2]_s$ and sixteen $[(90/0^0)_4]_s$ plies panels. Each ply was 0.125 mm thick for the nominal fibre volume content 62%. Optical fibres were embedded in the middle plane or near the surface of the laminate.

In the second part of the experimental program, composite laminates were made from Fibredux 914 unidirectional carbon pre-preg with a fibre content of 59.45 %. In this case Optical Fibres were embedded below the surface and near the bottom of laminate. Laminates contained 0.24 % OFs. Note that in all cases, the OFs were aligned with the carbon reinforcing fibres and were placed between two plies of identical orientation.

Experimental and analytical studies have shown that this is optimal orientation to minimize the effect that the embedded optical fiber has on the surrounding host material, see Culshaw and Gardiner (1993). Optical Fibres were placed in the mid-plane of the laminate, or below the surface ply and aligned with the fibre direction to the 0^0 -plies. Further details of the preparation of these specimens are given in Hadzic (2000).

Table 1 Laminates (AS4/3501-6) Tested -Tensile Test

Laminate	Optical Fibres	Specimens
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	Diameter (μm)	Number of Optical Fibres	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Gauge Length (mm)
$[(90/0^{\circ})_2]_s$	250	N/A	30	1	80
$[(90/0^{\circ})_2 - \text{OF2}]_s$	250	2	30	1.35	80
$[(90/0^{\circ})_2 - \text{OF5}]_s$	250	5	30	1.35	80
$[(90/0^{\circ})_2 - \text{OF9}]_s$	250	9	30	1.35	80
$[(90/0^{\circ})_4]_s$	250	N/A	30	2.36	80
$[(90/0^{\circ})_4 - \text{OF2}]_s$	250	2	30	2.36	80
$[(90/0^{\circ})_4 - \text{OF5}]_s$	250	5	30	2.36	80
$[(90/0^{\circ})_4 - \text{OF9}]_s$	250	9	30	2.36	80

EXPLANATION OF THE LAMINATE ID CODING

$[(90/0^{\circ})_2]_s$ - Symmetrical Specimen with 8plys (alternate orientation at 90° and 0°)

$[(90/0^{\circ})_4 - \text{OF2}]_s$ Symmetric laminate (16 layers) with 2 Optical Fibres embedded in middle plane

$[(90/0^{\circ})_4 - \text{OF9}]_s$ Symmetric laminate (16 layers) with 9 Optical Fibres embedded in middle plane

IMPACT TESTS

Impact testing was undertaken using a standard drop-weight test rig width (s) a 12 mm and nominal mass (m_1) 1769.8 g, spherically-nosed weight falling through a height of 1400 mm to strike the panels centrally. Prepared specimens had dimensions 115mm x 90mm. National Instrument SCXI-1000 DC equipment has been used for the test and more details of this test process can be obtained from Hadzic(2000).

VICOTEX (914/42) was also used in the impact test studies and the results are shown below. Preparation of specimens for the impact energy to fracture testing was made using the same procedure as described in Hadzic (2000). However the dimensions of the specimens and the number of optical fibers embedded are altered slightly as shown in Table 2 below.

The specimens had the dimensions of 115mm length by 90mm width. The equipment used for the test was SCXI-1000 DC. The data was recorded using the Pulsecent VI program.

Table 2 Results of Impact Energy-for-Fracture tests

<i>Laminate</i>	<i>Specimens tested</i>	<i>Mass (g)</i>	<i>Difference between Pulses (P2-P1)</i>	<i>Fracture Energy (U) Joule</i>

$[(90/0^0)_2]_s$	3	1500	0.37617	17.541
$[(90/0^0)_2 - \text{OF8}]_s$	3	1500	0.38557	17.4803
$[(90/0^0)_2 - \text{OF15}]_s$	3	1500	0.39069	17.4331
$[(90/0^0)_2 - \text{OF29}]_s$	3	1500	0.47309	16.5230
$[(90/0^0)_2]_s$	3	1500	0.21508	17.2522
$[(90/0^0)_4 - \text{OF8}]_s$	3	1500	0.2102	17.1357
$[(90/0^0)_4 - \text{OF15}]_s$	3	1500	0.20528	17.002
$[(90/0^0)_4 - \text{OF29}]_s$	3	1500	0.1977	16.7626
$[0/0/90/0^0]_s$	3	1500	0.4262	17.0764
$[0/0 - \text{OF72}/0/90/0/0/90/0/0 - \text{OF72}/0^0]$	3	1500	0.51219	15.9361

The presence of Optical Fibres once again effected the mechanical properties of the composite laminates. As shown in Table 2, the increase of OF in the identical unidirectional composite specimens reduced the fracture energy required of the composite material.

Plotting such results (Figure 1) derives similar relationship to that for the Tensile tests reported in Hadzic (2000) and Hadzic *et al* (1999). As seen in Figure 1 there is a drop in the fracture energy with increased number of Optical Fibres. A more significant effect is shown in the last 2 rows of Table 2. Here, 72 Optical Fibre strands were placed near the top and bottom of the specimen ($[0/0 - \text{OF72}/0/90/0/0/90/0/0 - \text{OF72}/0^0]$) and the energy for fracture drops from 17.07 to 15.9 J.

Figure 1 Fracture Energy Vs Number of Emebedded Optical Fibres

ANALYTICAL MODELLING

In this section, the exposition of embedded fibre-optic induced damage is provided using continuum mechanics and energy balance principles.

Assuming orthotropic material properties and plane stress conditions, the stiffness matrix generalised by Hooke's law relation is modified to allow for the fibre-optic inserts as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{11} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix}_{\text{Damaged}} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{11} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix}_{\text{Without Fibre - Optic Inserts}} - \begin{bmatrix} \Theta_{11} & \Theta_{12} & 0 \\ \Theta_{11} & \Theta_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Theta_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

(1)

Where Θ is a stiffness loss parameter similar to that described by Zhang and Soutis (1992) as an *in-situ* damage effective function (IDEF).

If the tested samples in this study are schematically represented as shown below in Figure 2, then the following analytical considerations can be introduced.

Figure 2 A cross-sectional schematic of the composite panel tested in this study (not to scale)

The general stress-strain relationship is

$$\sigma_{ij} = 2\mu e_{ij} + \lambda\delta_{ij} e_{kk} \quad (2)$$

Where μ and λ are Lamé's constants and are defined below. σ is the induced stress and e is the strain. δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta as defined by Segal (1987).

$$\mu = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)} \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda = \frac{E\nu}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \quad (3)$$

E and ν are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio respectively.

STRAIN ENERGY DECOMPOSITION

The total volume of the composite under consideration is V and that for an individual resin-rich eyelet plus an optical fibre is Γ . If the outstanding 'unaffected' composite volume is Ω , the general strain energy decomposition equation for the case shown in Figure 2 is:

$$\int_V \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) dV = \int_{\Omega} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Omega + \sum_1^n \int_{\Gamma} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Gamma \quad (4)$$

where n is the number of resin-rich eyelets.

Equation (2) above assumes perfect bonding between the optical fibre and the polymer matrix composite. At this stage of the analysis, no disbonds or material imperfections are assumed to be present.

When Equation (2) is substituted into the LHS of Equation (4) and after integrating, the overall strain energy, U, is:

$$U = \int_V \left(\mu e_{ij} e_{ij} + \frac{\lambda}{2} e_{kk}^2 \right) dV \quad (5)$$

Introducing the damage entity tensor, d_{ij} , described by Talreja (1991),

$$d_{ij} = \int_S a_i n_j dS \quad (6)$$

Where a and n are 'activity' and normal vectors acting on the surface S. The damage mode tensor is thus defined as:

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{k=1}^m \left[(d_{ij})_k \right] \quad (7)$$

Where m is the number of identifiable damage zones.

From the markedly diminished failure load for the densely packed optical fibre placements shown in Table 2, it appears a transformation of entities takes place when deformation occurs as proposed in Equation (8) below. Here, the strain energy component of the resin -rich eyelet as described in Equation (4) gets transformed to either the stiffness reduction entity described in Equation (1) and/or the damage mode entity tensor described in Equation (7).

$$\sum_1^n \int_{\Gamma} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Gamma \Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} D_{ij} = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{k=1}^m \left[(d_{ij})_k \right] \\ \left[\begin{array}{ccc} \Theta_{11} & \Theta_{12} & 0 \\ \Theta_{11} & \Theta_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Theta_{66} \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

It is this transformation in Equation (8) that is thought to be responsible for the degradation in mechanical properties as shown in Table 2. Here, compared to other samples, the OF density is dramatically increased and the OFs are relocated from the centre to near the surface.

ENERGY RELEASE RATE CONSIDERATIONS

If the damage entities develop into micro-cracks, the overall potential energy, PE of the element under consideration reduces to:

$$PE = U_T - U_{Fracture} \quad (9.)$$

Using Equation (5.9), Equation (5.14) expands to:

$$PE = \int_{\Omega} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Omega + \sum_1^n \int_{\Gamma} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Gamma - \alpha \left(\sum_1^n \int_{\Gamma} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Gamma \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\therefore PE = \int_{\Omega} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Omega + \sum_1^n \int_{\Gamma} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Gamma (1 - \alpha) \quad (11)$$

where

$$\alpha \left(\sum_1^n \int_{\Gamma} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Gamma \right)$$

is the proportion of the resin-rich eyelet related strain energy that has been ‘released’ due to cracking.

The energy release rate, G is equal to the 1st partial derivative of PE with regard to the cracked surface area under a fixed load, Zhang *et al* (1992b). Hence:

$$G = \left. \frac{\partial(PE)}{\partial A} \right|_{\sigma} \quad (12)$$

Substituting Equation (17) into (18),

$$G = \frac{\partial \left(\int_{\Omega} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Omega \right)}{\partial A} + \frac{(1 - \alpha) \partial \left(\int_0^n \sum_1^n \int_{\Gamma} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Gamma \right)}{\partial A} \quad (13)$$

If Equation (13) can be evaluated and plotted against a damage entity such as Equation (7) or a parameter such as cracks per unit volume, then a fracture-related parameter such as G can be represented as in a resistance (R) curve, as shown by Zhang *et al* (1992b). This can be used to characterise a laminate’s resistance to ‘damage’ with embedded Optical Fibres.

It is argued that,

$$\alpha \left(\sum_1^n \int_{\Gamma} \left(\int_0^{e_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} de_{ij} \right) d\Gamma \right)$$

in Equation (11) is partly responsible for the decrease in energy to fracture due to Optical Fibres as shown in Table 2 and Figure 1.

CONCLUSION

This study provides a unique look at the structural integrity analysis of composite structures with embedded Optical Fibres with Impact energy results. In this paper, it has been shown categorically that some amount of deterioration occurs when Optical Fibres are integrated in composite structures, especially when placed close to the surface. This near-surface placement test parameter is significant in that, for sensing applications in structural components, this will be the preferred position in order to effectively capture the stress and strain changes.

This analysis calls for caution in the use of Optical Fibres in composite structures where the accepted tenet is that 'embedding Optical Fibres is perfectly safe in composite structures when deployed under general guidelines'.

An energy release-rate component directly attributable to the resin-rich weakness zones has been identified and modelled. The challenge remains how to further quantify this parameter and compare it directly to the experimentally determined fracture energies.

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